

**ADJUVANT EFFECTS OF THE FASCIAL DISTORTION MODEL IN PATIENTS
WITH TEMPOROMANDIBULAR DISORDERS: A MULTI-CENTERED
RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED CLINICAL TRIAL**

Harun Gençosmanoğlu ⁴

¹Karabük University, Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Karabük, Türkiye.

²Hacettepe University, Institute of Health Sciences, Department of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Ankara, Türkiye.

³Bolu Abant İzzet Baysal University, Faculty of Dentistry, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Bolu, Türkiye.

⁴Hacettepe University, Faculty of Physical Therapy and Rehabilitation, Department of Musculoskeletal Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, Ankara, Türkiye.

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to compare the effects of the fascial distortion model with the Pilates method or control in patients with temporomandibular disorders. The intervention groups received one of these two methods in addition to the conventional home program (patient education and Rocabado's 6x6 home exercises), while the control group did not receive any treatment. Fifty-four patients (eighteen per group) were recruited for eight weeks. Pain intensity was measured with the revised graded chronic pain scale, short-form McGill pain questionnaire, visual analog scale, and numerical pain rating scale. Head posture was assessed by photogrammetry. Maximum pain-free mouth opening, maximum possible mouth opening, maximum assisted mouth opening, laterotrusions, and protrusion were measured using a digital vernier caliper. Temporomandibular disorder severity, dysfunction, disability, and quality of life were assessed by the Fonseca anamnestic index, the mandibular function impairment questionnaire, the craniofacial pain and disability inventory, and the cognitive exercise therapy approach-

biopsychosocial questionnaire, respectively. The group-by-time interaction effect was only statistically significant for right laterotrusion ($F = 4.66$, $p = .012$), left laterotrusion ($F = 3.703$, $p = .034$), pain intensity in the last week according to the numeric pain rating scale and the short-form McGill pain questionnaire ($\chi^2 = 2.84e+6$, $p < .001$; $F = 4.158$, $p < .001$; respectively), present pain intensity according to the visual analog scale and the index on the short-form McGill pain questionnaire ($F = 5.078$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2 = 29.74$, $p < .001$; respectively), temporomandibular disorder severity ($F = 3.38$, $p = .044$), and disability in jaw functional status ($F = 3.4721$, $p = .044$). Once-per-week sessions of the fascial distortion model, combined with the conventional home program, clinically and/or statistically significantly improved maximum pain-free mouth opening, laterotrusions, present pain intensity, and pain intensity in the last week, temporomandibular disorder severity, dysfunction, and disability.

Keywords: Temporomandibular Disorders, Musculoskeletal Manipulations, Pilates-Based Exercises, Pain Measurement, Disability Evaluation, Posture

Funding: This study was financially supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye through the 2211-A National PhD Scholarship Program.

INTRODUCTION

Temporomandibular disorders are of common interest to physiotherapists, dentists, and medical doctors from various fields. Temporomandibular disorders are conditions/disorders affecting the temporomandibular joint, masticatory muscles, and surrounding structures (Gençosmanoğlu et al., 2024). Manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model was proposed by American osteopath emergency physician Stephen Typaldos in 1991 (Capistrant et al., 2021; Kollarics et al., 2024; Nagel, 2014; Typaldos, 2002). The Pilates method is also a modern exercise method based on core stabilization training developed by the German physical trainer Joseph Hubertus Pilates in the 20th century (Li et al., 2024; Malode & Vijay, 2023; Pearce & Sessa, 2022). According to the

authors' knowledge, the effects of the fascial distortion model and Pilates-based core stability training on head posture, temporomandibular range of motion, pain intensity, severity, dysfunction, disability, and quality of life have not been investigated. This is the first study to investigate the effects of the fascial distortion model in addition to conventional treatment, the core stabilization training in addition to conventional treatment, and no treatment on head posture, temporomandibular range of motion, pain intensity, temporomandibular disorder severity, dysfunction, disability, and quality of life, considering group by time interaction effect.

The present study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of adding manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model by comparing it with the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method or non-interventional control in patients with temporomandibular disorders. The research questions of the present study are as follows:

- Is the effectiveness of adding the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model to conventional home therapy different from the addition of the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method to conventional home therapy?
- Is the effectiveness of the combination of manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model and conventional home therapy different from non-interventional control?
- Is the effectiveness of the combination of the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method and conventional home therapy different from non-interventional control?

The alternative hypotheses of this trial are as follows:

- The group-by-time interaction effect for eye-tragus-horizontal angle was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for pogonion-tragus-C₇ angle was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the

conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.

- The group-by-time interaction effect for tragus-C₇-horizontal angle was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for tragus-C₇-shoulder angle was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for shoulder-C₇-horizontal angle was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for shoulder-C₇-horizontal angle was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for maximum pain-free mouth opening was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for maximum possible mouth opening was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in

addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.

- The group-by-time interaction effect for maximum assisted mouth opening was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for right laterotrusion was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for left laterotrusion was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for protrusion was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for present pain intensity was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for pain intensity in the last week was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates

method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.

- The group-by-time interaction effect for chronic pain intensity was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for temporomandibular disorder severity was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for temporomandibular dysfunction was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for temporomandibular disability was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.
- The group-by-time interaction effect for health-related quality of life was significant between the manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model in addition to the conventional home therapy, the core stabilization training based on the Pilates method in addition to the conventional home therapy, and the non-intervention control.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Trial design

The present study is a randomized, controlled, parallel-group, three-armed, multi-centered, unblinded clinical trial. It was reported according to Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (Schulz et al., 2010) (Figure 1).

Ethics

The present study followed the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Ethical Committee for Non-Invasive Clinical Research of Karabük University (Decision number: 2023/1360)

Participants

Fifty-four patients (18 per group) were recruited. Inclusion criteria were decided as (1) a three-month temporomandibular joint complaint, (2) a diagnosis of temporomandibular disorders based on Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (Schiffman et al., 2014) confirmed by radiological examination, (3) age between 18 and 64 years, and (4) comprehension and interest in responding to assessment questionnaires. Exclusion criteria were decided as (1) a history of any trauma that may have affected cranial, cervical, or facial region, (2) any surgical or radiotherapeutic intervention in cranial, cervical, or facial region in the previous six months, (3) any surgical, medical, or physiotherapeutic interventions for temporomandibular disorders in the last month, (4) pregnancy or breastfeeding, (5) exercise therapy for head posture for the last month, and (6) a systemic condition (neurological, rheumatological, oncological, etc.) that could affect the temporomandibular joint or interfere with the evaluation.

Figure 1. Flow diagram according to Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials. FDM: Fascial distortion model group. CST: Core stabilization training group. CG: Control group.

Interventions

Patients in the intervention group received manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model or core stabilization training based on the Pilates method for about 45 minutes once a week for eight weeks in addition to conventional home therapy, while the control group received no treatment. The conventional home therapy consisted of Rocabado's 6x6 exercises (Sahin et al., 2021; Seyhan & Atalay, 2023) and patient education. The principal investigator was trained and certified as a practitioner of the fascial distortion model according to the European Fascial Distortion Model Association regulations and a Pilates instructor according to the regulations of the Turkish Gymnastics Federation. The principal investigator provided all treatments.

Outcomes

Pain intensity of the temporomandibular and cervical regions was assessed using the Revised Graded Chronic Pain Scale (Şentürk et al., 2022; Von Korff et al., 2020) for chronic pain, Visual Analog Scale (Begum & Hossain, 2019) for present pain, Numeric Pain Rating Scale (Stijic et al., 2024) for pain in the last week, Short Form McGill Pain Questionnaire (Melzack, 1987; Yakut et al., 2007) for pain in the last week and index of Short Form McGill Pain Questionnaire (Melzack, 1987; Yakut et al., 2007) for present pain. Head posture was assessed via eye-tragus-horizontal angle, pogonion-tragus-C₇ angle, tragus-C₇-horizontal angle, tragus-C₇-shoulder angle, and shoulder-C₇-horizontal angle using photogrammetry (Figure 2) (Gençosmanoğlu et al., 2024). In addition, maximum pain-free mouth opening, maximum possible mouth opening, maximum assisted mouth opening, laterotrusions, and protrusion were measured using a digital vernier caliper (Figure 3) (Best et al., 2013; Gençosmanoğlu & Yılmaz, 2024). Temporomandibular disorder severity, temporomandibular dysfunction, temporomandibular disability and health-related quality of life were assessed using the Fonseca Anamnestic Index (Arikan et al., 2024; Fonseca et al., 1994; Kaynak et al., 2023), the Mandibular Function Impairment Questionnaire (Stegenga et al., 1993; Yıldız et al., 2024), the Craniofacial Pain and Disability Inventory (Arikan et al., 2023; La Touche et al., 2014) and the Cognitive Exercise Therapy Approach-Biopsychosocial Questionnaire (Ünal et al., 2017), respectively. All variables were measured at baseline and 8th week, and pain intensity was additionally measured at 2nd, 4th and 6th week.

Figure 2. Photogrammetry of head posture. (1) Eye-tragus-horizontal angle. (2) Pogonion-tragus-C₇ angle. (3) Tragus-C₇-horizontal angle. (4) Tragus-C₇-shoulder angle. (5) Shoulder-C₇-horizontal angle.

Sample size and power

The size of a future randomized controlled trial should be related to the sample size of a pilot study (Whitehead et al., 2016). Based on 95% power, 5% significance level, and the effect size ($\eta^2p = .089$) from an internal pilot study of this trial, the minimum required sample size was calculated as 45 based on two-way analysis of variance for repeated measures (group-time interaction). With a dropout rate of 20%, the present study was designed to be carried out with a total of 54 patients, 18 in each group (Faul et al., 2007).

Randomization

Random assignment was based on sequential permuted block randomization via a web-based application (sealedenvelope.com). Patients were randomly assigned to groups with a 1:1:1 allocation ratio in permuted blocks of sizes 6, 9, and 12. Patients, treatment practitioner and evaluator were not blinded.

Figure 3. A digital vernier caliper is used to measure the range of motion of temporomandibular joints.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out in Jamovi version 2.5.5 according to the intention-to-treat principle (*The jamovi project (2024). jamovi. (Version 2.5.5) [Computer Software].*). A significant level was accepted as $p < .05$. The normal distribution assumption was tested using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Descriptive statistics of continuous variables were presented as mean \pm standard deviation and median (minimum; maximum). Categorical variables were reported as quantity (n) and percentage. A two-way mixed analysis of variance and a generalized mixed linear model was conducted for continuous and categorical data to compare repeated measures between the three groups, respectively. The analysis

included right laterotrusion measured at baseline as covariance. The partial eta squared (η^2_p) value was calculated as effect size.

RESULTS

The group-by-time interaction effect was only statistically significant for right laterotrusion ($F = 4.66$, $p = .012$), left laterotrusion ($F = 3.703$, $p = .034$), pain intensity in the last week according to the numeric pain rating scale and the short-form McGill pain questionnaire ($\chi^2 = 2.84e+6$, $p < .001$; $F = 4.158$, $p < .001$; respectively), present pain intensity according to the visual analog scale and the index on the short-form McGill pain questionnaire ($F = 5.078$, $p < .001$; $\chi^2 = 29.74$, $p < .001$; respectively), temporomandibular disorder severity ($F = 3.38$, $p = .044$), and disability in jaw functional status ($F = 3.4721$, $p = .044$) (Table 1).

Table 1. Significant group-by-time interaction effects and effect sizes

<i>Measure</i>	<i>Group-by-time interaction effects</i>		<i>Effect sizes</i>
	<i>Statistics</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>η^2_p</i>
Right laterotrusion	$F = 4.66$.012	.098
Left laterotrusion	$F = 3.703$.034	.160
Pain intensity in the last week (Numeric pain rating scale)	$\chi^2 = 2.84e+6$	< .001	-
Pain intensity in the last week (Short-form McGill pain questionnaire)	$F = 4.158$	< .001	.165
Present pain intensity (Visual analog scale)	$F = 5.078$	< .001	.197
Present pain intensity (Index of short-form McGill pain questionnaire)	$\chi^2 = 29.74$	< .001	-
Temporomandibular disorder severity	$F = 3.38$.044	.142
Disability in jaw functional status	$F = 3.4721$.044	.185

DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of adding manual therapy based on the fascial distortion model by comparing it with the core stabilization training based

on the Pilates method or non-interventional control in patients with temporomandibular disorders. Group-by-time interaction effects were statistically significant on right laterotrusion, left laterotrusion, pain intensity in the last week, present pain intensity, temporomandibular disorder severity, and disability in jaw functional status.

There are some limitations in this study. The first limitation is that patients were not diagnosed according to temporomandibular subgroups. Secondly, it was not blinded. Thirdly, it did not contain long-term follow-ups.

CONCLUSION

Once-per-week sessions of the fascial distortion model, combined with the conventional home program, clinically and/or statistically significantly improved maximum pain-free mouth opening, laterotrusions, present pain intensity, and pain intensity in the last week, temporomandibular disorder severity, dysfunction, and disability.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present study was financially supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye through the 2211-A National PhD Scholarship Program.

REFERENCES

Arikan, H., Citaker, S., & Ucok, C. (2023). Cross-cultural adaptation, reliability, and validity of the Turkish version of the Craniofacial Pain and Disability Inventory (CF-PDI/T) for individuals with temporomandibular disorders. *Disabil Rehabil*, *45*(3), 523-533.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2022.2028909>

Arikan, H., Citaker, S., & Ucok, C. (2024). Psychometric properties of the Fonseca Anamnestic Index (FAI) for temporomandibular disorders: Turkish version, responsiveness, reliability, and validity study. *Disabil Rehabil*, *46*(7), 1408-1415.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2023.2199221>

- Begum, M. R., & Hossain, M. A. (2019). Validity and reliability of visual analogue scale (VAS) for pain measurement. *Journal of Medical Case Reports and Reviews*, 2(11), 394-402.
- Best, N., Best, S., Loudovici-Krug, D., & Smolenski, U. C. (2013). Measurement of Mandible Movements Using a Vernier Caliper – An Evaluation of the Intrasession-, Intersession- and Interobserver Reliability. *Cranio®*, 31(3), 176-180. <https://doi.org/10.1179/crn.2013.028>
- Capistrant, T., Harrer, G., & Pentzer, T. (2021). *The Fascial Distortion Model: Philosophy, Principles and Clinical Applications*. Handspring Publishing.
- Faul, F., Erdfelder, E., Lang, A. G., & Buchner, A. (2007). G*Power 3: a flexible statistical power analysis program for the social, behavioral, and biomedical sciences. *Behav Res Methods*, 39(2), 175-191. <https://doi.org/10.3758/bf03193146>
- Fonseca, D. M. d., Bonfante, G., Valle, A. L. d., & Freitas, S. F. T. d. (1994). Diagnóstico pela anamnese da disfunção craniomandibular. *RGO (Porto Alegre)*, 42(1), 23-28.
- Gençosmanoğlu, H., Ünlüer, N. Ö., Akin, M. E., Demir, P., & Aydın, G. (2024). An investigation of biomechanics, muscle performance, and disability level of craniocervical region of individuals with temporomandibular disorder. *Cranio®*, 42(2), 232-242. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08869634.2021.1938854>
- Gençosmanoğlu, H., & Yılmaz, E. (2024, 25.03.2024). Validity and Reliability of Digital Vernier Caliper in the Evaluation of Temporomandibular Joint Mobility in Patients with Temporomandibular Disorder: A Preliminary Report. 6th International Acharaka Congress On Medicine, Nursing, Midwifery, And Health Sciences, İzmir, Türkiye.
- The jamovi project (2024). jamovi. (Version 2.5.5) [Computer Software].* <https://www.jamovi.org>
- Kaynak, B. A., Taş, S., & Salkın, Y. (2023). The accuracy and reliability of the Turkish version of the Fonseca anamnestic index in temporomandibular disorders. *Cranio®*, 41(1), 78-83.
- Kollarics, A., Gençosmanoğlu, H., Biró, E., Zámbo, É. L., Király, B., & Hanzel, A. (2024). Effects of manual therapy on fascial distortion model in adolescent ankle sprain: a pilot study. *Journal of Chiropractic Medicine*.
- La Touche, R., Pardo-Montero, J., Gil-Martínez, A., Paris-Aleman, A., Angulo-Díaz-Parreño, S., Suárez-Falcón, J. C., Lara-Lara, M., & Fernández-Carnero, J. (2014). Craniofacial pain and

disability inventory (CF-PDI): development and psychometric validation of a new questionnaire. *Pain Physician*, 17(1), 95-108.

Li, M. F., Dev, D. R. D. O., Soh, P. D. K. G., Wang, M. C., & Yuan, M. Y. (2024). Effects of Pilates on body posture: a systematic review. *Archives of Rehabilitation Research and Clinical Translation*, 100345. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.arrct.2024.100345>

Malode, G. S., & Vijay, K. (2023). Pilates versus Bruegger's exercises for forward head posture associated with temporomandibular joint dysfunction. *Comparative Exercise Physiology*, 19(3), 253-264. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3920/CEP220055>

Melzack, R. (1987). The short-form McGill pain questionnaire. *Pain*, 30(2), 191-197.

Nagel, M. (2014). *The fascial distortion model by Stephen Typaldos D.O.: The Typaldos method*. European Fascial Distortion Model Association.

Pearce, K., & Sessa, S. (2022). *Rehabilitation Through Pilates: A Guide to Recovery from Common Musculo-Skeletal Conditions*. Aeon Books.

Sahin, D., Kaya Mutlu, E., Sakar, O., Ates, G., Inan, S., & Taskiran, H. (2021). The effect of the ischaemic compression technique on pain and functionality in temporomandibular disorders: A randomised clinical trial. *J Oral Rehabil*, 48(5), 531-541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joor.13145>

Schiffman, E., Ohrbach, R., Truelove, E., Look, J., Anderson, G., Goulet, J. P., List, T., Svensson, P., Gonzalez, Y., Lobbezoo, F., Michelotti, A., Brooks, S. L., Ceusters, W., Drangsholt, M., Ettlin, D., Gaul, C., Goldberg, L. J., Haythornthwaite, J. A., Hollender, L., . . . Dworkin, S. F. (2014). Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders (DC/TMD) for Clinical and Research Applications: recommendations of the International RDC/TMD Consortium Network* and Orofacial Pain Special Interest Group†. *J Oral Facial Pain Headache*, 28(1), 6-27. <https://doi.org/10.11607/jop.1151>

Schulz, K. F., Altman, D. G., & Moher, D. (2010). CONSORT 2010 statement: updated guidelines for reporting parallel group randomized trials. *Ann Intern Med*, 152(11), 726-732. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-152-11-201006010-00232>

Seyhan, M., & Atalay, E. S. (2023). Is core stability training effective in temporomandibular disorder? A randomized controlled trial. *Clin Oral Investig*, 27(12), 7237-7246. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00784-023-05274-x>

Stegenga, B., de Bont, L. G., de Leeuw, R., & Boering, G. (1993). Assessment of mandibular function impairment associated with temporomandibular joint osteoarthritis and internal derangement. *J Orofac Pain*, *7*(2), 183-195.

Stijic, M., Messerer, B., Meißner, W., & Avian, A. (2024). Numeric rating scale for pain should be used in an ordinal but not interval manner. A retrospective analysis of 346,892 patient reports of the quality improvement in postoperative pain treatment registry. *Pain*, *165*(3), 707-714. https://journals.lww.com/pain/fulltext/2024/03000/numeric_rating_scale_for_pain_should_be_used_in_an.22.aspx

Şentürk, İ. A., Aşkın Turan, S., Şentürk, E., & İcen, N. K. (2022). Validation, reliability, and cross-cultural adaptation study of Graded Chronic Pain Scale Revised into Turkish in patients with primary low back pain. *Pain Practice*, *22*(3), 306-321.

Typaldos, S. (2002). *FDM: Clinical and theoretical application of the fascial distortion model within the practice of medicine and surgery*. Orthopathic Global Health Publications.

Ünal, E., Arın, G., Karaca, N. B., Kiraz, S., Akdoğan, A., Kalyoncu, U., Ertenli, A. İ., Apraş Bilgen, Ş., Karadağ, Ö., Erden, A., Kılıç, L., Göksülük, D., Karabulut, E., Yakut, Y., & Alpar, R. (2017). Romatizmalı hastalar için bir yaşam kalitesi ölçeğinin geliştirilmesi: madde havuzunun oluşturulması [Development of a quality of life measurement for rheumatic patients: item pool construction]. *Journal of Exercise Therapy and Rehabilitation*, *4*(2), 67-75. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/jetr/issue/41778/504344>

Von Korff, M., DeBar, L. L., Krebs, E. E., Kerns, R. D., Deyo, R. A., & Keefe, F. J. (2020). Graded chronic pain scale revised: mild, bothersome, and high-impact chronic pain. *Pain*, *161*(3), 651-661.

Whitehead, A. L., Julious, S. A., Cooper, C. L., & Campbell, M. J. (2016). Estimating the sample size for a pilot randomised trial to minimise the overall trial sample size for the external pilot and main trial for a continuous outcome variable. *Stat Methods Med Res*, *25*(3), 1057-1073. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0962280215588241>

Yakut, Y., Yakut, E., Bayar, K., & Uygur, F. (2007). Reliability and validity of the Turkish version short-form McGill pain questionnaire in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *Clinical rheumatology*, *26*(7), 1083-1087.